

Reservoir computing with associative neuronal assemblies: one network to rule them all

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ABSTRACT

The brain is a complex dynamical system that in order to function properly needs to encode and decode external information with an high degree of accuracy and resilience. To do so it is essential to memorize familiar stimuli and recall them if necessary. Hebbian learning allows to store associative memories as stable fixed-points, or attractors, of recurrent neural networks with symmetric synaptic couplings. However, realistic memories are not static pictures but rather complex dynamical sequences. On the other hand, reservoir computing is a reinforcement learning technique that allows to learn complex sequences harnessing the nonlinearity of recurrent networks but it is mostly assumed to work only with highly asymmetric networks. Our main result is to show that it is indeed possible to implement the reservoir computing paradigm with associative networks bridging the gap between two pillars of theoretical neuroscience. Leveraging the analytical tractability of these models, we formulate a complete theory explaining the mechanisms by which these networks learn to mimic arbitrary dynamical systems and even predict optimal parameters to successfully reproduce them. As an application we show how this model is capable to store multiple dynamical systems in different attractors and recall them with a context which is solely given by the initial condition.

1 Introduction

In the general framework of the reservoir computing¹⁻³, recurrent neural networks exploit the relatively high dimensionality of the collective dynamics displayed in response to an external input. The aim is to find a linear read-out of the network state capable to reproduce the input. If such linear combination exists, the read-out variable can then be fed-back into the network by replacing the input and closing the loop. Assuming that the time series provided as input is derived from the state of a dynamical system, the ongoing activity of the closed-loop recurrent neural network (RNN) has been shown to be capable to emulate/predict the time evolution of the original system.

Such “emulative” capability relies on the dynamical richness the stimulated reservoir expresses, and it is granted by the asymmetric nature of the synaptic matrix \mathbf{W} connecting the elements of the RNN. Indeed, both under a condition of damped dynamics where the eigenvalues of \mathbf{W} have negative real parts, and under a chaotic dynamical regime of the network ongoing activity, a suited prescription of the feed-back implementing the closed-loop can successfully serves to the purpose of emulating the original driving system¹⁻³.

However, it is not known whether the high-dimensionality of the reservoir dynamics due to the asymmetric synaptic matrix is a really necessary ingredient for this task. Here, we address this question by investigating the reservoir computing capability of a paradigmatic RNN with symmetric couplings (namely, the Hopfield model) finding that indeed chaos and asymmetry are not needed. Moreover choosing symmetric couplings as a starting point one has several benefits. First of all in terms of explainability, we found that the properties of the energy landscape control whether or not the reservoir will be able to reproduce the target system in the autonomous phase. Secondly the network model we use is intrinsically low dimensional and this property is preserved even after training.

Attractor neural network have been historically of great importance in the development of theoretical neuroscience and on the study of complex system in general. In the years several indirect proof have been found that advocates for such real neural networks rely on this framework however most of the state of the art machine learning models do not really use this features to perform computation. One major limitations of traditional attractor neural network is the symmetry in the synapses which is not biologically plausible. Proving that reservoir computing is possible for these system also alleviate the issue with such symmetry, in fact after learning the synaptic matrix will inevitably contain also an asymmetric part which we found however to be a small perturbation. In other terms, the learning does not destroy the attractors already present in the network but will change their nature. This open the doors to all new ways of thinking about attractor neural networks. For example we will show that it is possible to recall entire dynamical trajectories in a context dependent way, a key feature of real intelligent systems.

Figure 1. Reservoir computing with symmetric synaptic interactions. a) The probability density of the eigenvalues, obtained over 300 realization, of $\hat{\xi}^T \hat{\xi} / N$ for different levels of α , in colors. In b) the schematics of reservoir computing approach, before learning first row the target signal, $x(t)$ of Lorenz system, is fed as a driving current to the network. After learning the read-out weights allows to close the loop and reproduce the target autonomously. In c) we show a successful case for the $x(t)$ of Lorenz. Until $t=20$ the network is driven by $x(t)$ in black. The read-out fits well $x(t) \sim \beta \bar{m}(t)$ in the learning phase (red dots). After $t=20$ network reproduce in autonomy the target $x(t)$ (red). Thanks to Takens theorem even if we trained the network only on $x(t)$ we can reconstruct the entire chaotic attractor (d).

2 The model

2.1 Recurrent neural networks

As reservoir we consider a relatively standard recurrent neural network (RNN) aiming to model the multiscale organization of biological networks of neurons in the mammalian brains. In this modeling framework, microscopic neurons are clustered in local mesoscopic modules (i.e., the cortical columns) which exchange their lump activity $r_i(t)$ – i.e. the spike firing rate of the i -th module – through a coupling matrix $W_{ij} = \{\mathbf{W}\}_{ij}$ (namely, the synaptic/connectivity matrix). The activity of the i -th module in the network is driven by the input current (i.e., the field) it receives:

$$h_i(t) = \sum_{j=1}^N W_{ij} r_j(t) + h_{\text{ext},i}(t), \quad (1)$$

a linear combination of the N pre-synaptic firing rates and an additional input current $h_{\text{ext},i}(t)$ received from the external environment and by other upstream networks.

The single-module dynamics is determined by the input-output nonlinear amplification $\Phi(h_i)$ of the current which in turn drives the change in time of the firing activity as

$$\tau \dot{\vec{r}} = \Phi(\vec{h}) - \vec{r} = \Phi(\vec{r}, \vec{h}_{\text{ext}}) - \vec{r}. \quad (2)$$

Starting from the seminal works of Grossberg and Wilson & Cowan⁴, this system of N first-order ordinary differential equations (ODEs) has been widely used in theoretical neuroscience to describe the dynamics of biological networks of neurons⁵⁻⁸. In what follows, the relaxation time scale τ usually spanning few tens of milliseconds sets the time unit.

The network dynamics (2) is a “rate-based” description of the evolution in time of the network activity. In^{9,10}, such dynamics has been proven to be equivalent to the “current-based” dynamics of RNN with graded neurons⁵, widely used in statistical mechanics¹¹⁻¹³. Analogously to these works, we adopt the following sigmoidal input-output gain function

$$\{\Phi(r, h_{\text{ext}})\}_i = \Phi(h_i) \equiv \tanh h_i(t) \quad (3)$$

with $h_i(t)$ given by Eq. (1).

2.2 Symmetric reservoir

To investigate whether symmetric synaptic matrices allows reservoir computing as the asymmetric ones, we resort to a paradigmatic RNN capable to store P patterns of activity $\vec{\xi}^\mu$ ($\mu \in [1, P]$) with randomly chosen elements $\xi_i^\mu = \{\pm 1\}$. This is the Hopfield model with graded response neurons following Eq. (2) and incorporating the Amari-Hopfield

synaptic matrix^{5,14,15}. If we define as $\hat{\xi}$ the $N \times P$ matrix whose columns are the pattern $\vec{\xi}^\mu$ the synaptic interaction matrix can be written as

$$\mathbf{W} = \mathbf{W}_{AH} \equiv \frac{g}{N} \hat{\xi}^T \hat{\xi}. \quad (4)$$

where we indicate with T the transpose. Note that \mathbf{W}_{AH} is a rank- P symmetric matrix. This is an important point we will stress in the next section to show that ‘‘symmetric’’ reservoir computing can be intrinsically low-dimensional. The total current that enters the gain function can be written as:

$$\vec{h} = \mathbf{W}_{AH} \vec{r} + \mathbf{W}_{in} \vec{I}$$

where we rewrite the non-recurrent part of the current as \vec{h}_{ext} the product of \mathbf{W}_{in} an $N \times D$ matrix where D is the dimension of the input and the input \vec{I} .

2.3 Low-dimensionality of symmetric reservoirs

In general, the dimensionality of this system is dictated by the number N of units composing the RNN. However, in the symmetric reservoir framework we introduced, the collective state of the network can wander fully confined into a subspace with dimension P , the number of pattern stored. the space provided that the network state (i.e., it is set to initial condition) This modeling framework allows us also to have a direct control on the intrinsic dimensionality of the reservoir, another degree of freedom of the problem which we want to test. Indeed, as the matrix \mathbf{W}_{AH} has rank- P one could expect the dynamics of the reservoir can be fully described in a suited subspace with dimension P , provided the external stimulation does not lead the RNN state outside such space pushing it towards an orthogonal direction. In fact the overlaps with patterns:

$$m_\mu = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N \xi_i^\mu r_i}{N}$$

have a close dynamical systems that can be derived directly from Eq. 2 applying the overlap definitions:

$$\dot{m}_\mu = \sum_{i=1}^N \frac{\xi_i^\mu \Phi(g \sum_v \xi_i^v m_v + I_i)}{N} - m_\mu \quad (5)$$

For this reason in the following we will fit the read-out β directly on the overlaps by minimizing $\|I(t) - \beta \vec{m}(t)\|$ in this way even in the autonomous phase the network remains confined in a P dimensional space. Note that the patterns are related to the rates by $\vec{m} = \hat{\xi} \vec{r} / N$, the complete readout matrix in the r -space is simply: $\mathbf{W}_{out} = \frac{\beta \hat{\xi}}{N}$.

2.4 Lyapunov function

Following^{5,16}, a Lyapunov function $E(r)$ (i.e., the energy stored into a dissipative system) can be worked out as.

$$\dot{E}(r) = \sum_{i=1}^N \frac{dE}{dr_i} \dot{r}_i = \frac{1}{\tau} \sum_{i=1}^N \frac{dE}{dr_i} (\Phi(h_i) - r_i) \leq 0$$

which is always fulfilled if

$$\frac{dE}{dr_i} = r_i - \Phi(h_i) \quad \forall i \in [1, N].$$

However we will use in the following the Lyapunov function in the patterns space which we found to be:

$$L(\{m_v\}) = \sum_{v=1}^P m_v^2 / 2 - \frac{1}{gN} \sum_{i=1}^N F \left(g \sum_v \xi_i^v m_v + h_{ext,i} \right) \quad (6)$$

where $F(x) = \log(\cosh(x))$ is the primitive of $\Phi(x)$. We will need also the local curvatures of any given attractor \vec{m} that are the eigenvalues of the Hessian of 6:

$$H_{\rho\gamma} = \delta_{\rho\gamma} - \frac{g}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \xi_i^\rho \xi_i^\gamma \Phi' \left(g \sum_v \xi_i^v m_v + h_{ext,i} \right)$$

Figure 2. Linking the complexity of the energy landscape to the performance of the AHRNN-based reservoir. a) Coefficient of variations c_v averaged over 50 trials ($N = 1000$) in the plane of self-interaction g and the memory load α . b) an AHRNN ($N=1000$) with $\alpha = 0.1$ and $g = 3$ is used. For this choice of parameters the energy landscape has minima with different level of roughness, i.e. heterogeneity of eigenvalues of the Hessian. Left panel, eigenvalues of the Hessian for different minima and the color code indicates the relative average error (over 50 trials) in reproducing autonomously the dynamics of the Lorenz attractor around that minimum. Right panel, relationship between c_v of eigenvalue distribution and the reproduction error. Error bars indicate 1 SEM. c) c_v of eigenvalue distribution varying the memory load α for $g = 2$ (black) and $g = 0.5$ (red). Shades indicate mean ± 3 SEM over 50 trials. Both the success rate (middle) and the stability time (right) behave like c_v .

3 Results

3.1 Reservoir computing with symmetric AHRNN and without chaos

Reservoir computing works only on reservoir with the echo-state property i.e. the capacity of the system to remember and reverberate an external input. This property has nothing to do with the synaptic structure chosen as starting point. Despite this fact, traditionally the scientific community has used network with fully random connections which are naturally asymmetric. Probably this idea comes from the realization that for weights extracted from a normal distribution with standard deviation $\sigma > 1$, i.e. the spectral radius, rate networks like (2) show chaotic behaviour around the unstable fixed point $\vec{r} = 0$. The best performances of vanilla RC have been found close to $\sigma \sim 1$ and the idea of computation at the 'edge-of-chaos' has gained considerable traction in the recent years. Here we want mainly to show that there is no need to choose the matrix to be asymmetric neither the starting activity of the network to be close to deterministic chaos to make the RC work. The synaptic matrix of the attractor network is in fact symmetric hence the eigenvalues are real. In Fig. 1 a we report the distribution of eigenvalues of \mathbf{W}_{AH} for different values of α . Applying the standard reservoir approach, Fig. 1 b for a sketch, we were able to reproduce autonomously the $x(t)$ of the Lorenz system, Fig. 1 c. Moreover, learning also the readout weights for $y(t)$ and $z(t)$ the reservoir reproduces the entire Lorenz attractor, Fig. 1 d, even though it was trained only on $x(t)$. This is characteristic of good reproduction of dynamical systems and it is explained by the Takens theorem.

3.2 Complex attractor states are needed to copy generic dynamical systems

Not all attractors are good for reservoir computing purposes. We found that the best predictor of whether or not a given attractor will allow for effective reproduction of the target dynamics is the roughness or complexity of the local energy landscape. The roughness of a minimum is characterized by the eigenvalue distribution of the Hessian i.e. the principal curvatures. The inverse of the curvature are the characteristic decay times of a given eigenmode close to the minimum. In other terms heterogeneous

Figure 3. Low-dimensional AHRNN are effective digital copies. a) An AHRNN of just 100 neurons with $P = 20$ patterns stored is capable of reproducing autonomously the $x(t)$ of Lorenz system. b) Time derivatives of x, y and z computed from the AHRNN-based reservoir are in linear relation with what is expected by the force field of the Lorenz system.

curvatures correspond to heterogeneous time scales expressed locally. A good way to parameterize this complexity is the coefficient of variation of the eigenvalues i.e. $c_v(\lambda) = \text{std}(\lambda)/\text{mean}(\lambda)$. We found that the success rate in reproducing the autonomous Lorenz chaotic trajectories and the stability time, i.e. the time needed to observe qualitative difference in target and reproduce autonomous dynamics are strongly correlated to the $c_v(\lambda)$ of the reference minimum i.e. the attractor chosen as initial condition in the learning phase. Based on this observation we can exclude entire regions of the parameters space as the minima are too simple to be used. For example in the classical recall state when α is small and $g > 1$. Recall attractors are states that have \vec{r} almost parallel to one of the patterns say $\vec{\xi}^\mu$. Then $m_\nu \sim \delta_{\mu,\nu}$ and all the eigenvalues approach $\lambda_n \tau \sim 1 - g\phi'(g)$ hence $c_v \sim 0$ the recall minima are perfect paraboloids. Even though these attractors are the best in terms of stability, since they are global minima, they are too simple to perform RC. In Fig. 2 a we chose $\alpha = 0.1$ and $g = 3$ which is close to the glassy phase transition. In this case it is easy to find a large set of minima of the 'recall' type and also 'spurious' minima. The eigenvalues spread largely differs. For all of them we performed 50 trials to reproduce $x(t)$ of Lorenz and computed the average relative error ε defined in the appendix. We found that $\varepsilon \sim 0$ only for those minima with c_v above a given threshold which depends on the complexity of the target trajectory. To investigate whether or not this holds for any value of g , and α we computed over 50 trials the success rate and the average stability time in two cases at $g = 2$ and $g=1/2$ for various levels of α . In both cases we found a striking correlation with the coefficient of variation, see Fig. 2 c.

3.3 Low-dimensional nature of AHRNN-based reservoir computing

We have already stressed that forcing the read-out weights on the overlaps \vec{m} has the great advantage to preserve the low dimensionality of the network even after learning. Combining these with the expressive power of the attractor network we show in Fig. 3 a that it is possible to reproduce the $x(t)$ of Lorenz with a network of just $N = 100$ and $P = 20$. Once the learning is finished the dynamics of the overlap can be integrated independently of the firing rate so the system is really just P dimensional. Low dimensional representations have been found in real neural systems and are usually preferred to high dimensional ones due to their relative resilience to noise. It is for this reason interesting that this concept naturally arises in our framework.

3.4 'Gravitational' computation: how dynamical systems are emulated

The main idea behind the reservoir computing on Amari-Hopfield network is that any dynamical system, even a non conservative one, can be recast as a gradient system (5) that is open, i.e. with time dependent drive. Note that recently a similar conclusion has been reached in the context of the Koopman framework and it has been shown that chaotic systems can be recast as driven linear systems¹⁷. To be more precise the driven phase, or learning phase, is initialized at $\vec{m}(t=0) = \vec{m}_s$ one of the many minima of the "free" Hopfield network ($I = 0$). At the next integration step the external current I will modify the energy landscape (6) changing both the topology, i.e. the local curvatures, and the position of the minima. Consequentially the system will feel a different gradient force and move accordingly following the 'center of mass', in analogy with gravitational systems. This mechanism will continue throughout the whole driven phase. Assuming that the dynamics is local, i.e. $|\vec{m}(t) - \vec{m}_s| \ll 1$, then the only information that is required for the system to work autonomously, i.e. after the learning period, is how the reference minimum needs to be moved. This is achieved using the standard approach of reservoir computing: a vector of read-out weights $\vec{\beta}$ is fitted to reproduce the signal, from the network activity, in the driven phase. Then the external current will be substituted by $I_x(t) = \vec{\beta} \cdot \vec{m}(t)$. In case of good fit however, the trajectories in the autonomous phase should be very close to those of the driven phase. Thus it should be possible to predict whether or not the reproduction will be stable and successful by studying the current dependent energy landscape in the driven phase. In Fig. 4 a we prove this point considering the reproduction of the Lorenz chaotic system. To better visualize the autonomous dynamics on the pattern space we performed PCA reduction on $\vec{m}(t)$ and we concentrate in the space of the first two PCAs in three different phases of the dynamics. The red

Figure 4. After learning, the reservoir is capable to reproduce the Lorenz chaotic attractor. For 3 different regions of the attractor (top figure) we followed the dynamics of the autonomous reservoir in the $m_n(t)$ space. To visualize the dynamics we performed a dimensional reduction using PCA on the overlaps and plotted in gray (bottom figures) the first two component. For each point in the time course we took the part of the synaptic current coming from the learned synapse and kept it constant. We then let the attractor network relax to it's closest minimum, given the constant bias term \vec{I} and obtained the manifold of fixed points (red line). This is the trajectory that the "center of gravity" of the dynamics follows. In fact the flux of the autonomous reservoir (black arrows) always points towards the centers of gravity which moves in time. In figure b) and c) we show respectively a success and a failure in autonomous reproduction. For both cases, in the first column the Lorenz system $x(t)$ is in black and the output of reservoir in red. The second column is the trajectory dependent distance of $\vec{m}(t)$ from the reference minimum. Last column is the current dependent minimum eigenvalue (black) and distance from the reference (red) as explained in the text. Note that in c) $\lambda_{min}(x) < 0$ for $|x| \sim 30$ and predicts the instability of the autonomous phase.

trajectory is obtained by clamping at each time step the value of the current $\vec{I}(t) = \vec{I}$ and letting the attractor network relax to equilibrium $\vec{m}_s(\vec{I})$, this will be the center of mass. We found, as expected that the time dependent force field always point towards the center of mass even in the autonomous phase. We can now use this information to predict failure in reproductions and understand the reason behind. In Fig. 4 b and c we report a successful and failed reproduction respectively. This kind of failed trial can be predicted beforehand using the curvatures of "adiabatic" reference minimum i.e. how \vec{m}_s changes as a function of \vec{I} . In particular we see that for the failed trial the minimum curvature λ_{min} changes abruptly for some values of the Lorenz x , which multiply the normalize vector \vec{I} . In these cases the the system will naturally go toward a new minimum far away from the reference one, see magenta traces. This happen either because $\vec{m}_s(x)$ become unstable along the minimal curvature direction or the basin of attraction of $\vec{m}_s(x)$ shrinks and some other fixed point becomes dominant. It is interesting to note that we can see that the failed trial loses stability in the proximity of $x \sim -20$ as can be predicted from the study of the minimal curvature.

We close this section with one final note. After learning the synaptic matrix changes $\mathbf{W} \rightarrow \mathbf{W}_{AH} + \frac{\beta \hat{\xi}}{N}$. The second term generally implement an irrotational component in the system force field. As a result the new coupling matrix will become asymmetric, however the degree of asymmetry must not be too high since the energy structure must be preserved to be able to use it in the reproduction of the signal.

3.5 Learning as a perturbation of the synaptic matrix

An important aspect that is often not considered when working with standard reservoir computing is how much the synaptic matrix is perturbed after training. Learning new things at the cost of forgetting what it was previously known is a common and central problem in machine learning. In this section we ask how large this perturbation is in the plane (g, α) . Consider for simplicity the case where the target $x(t)$ is one-dimensional. Given that we perform the linear readout on the overlaps \vec{m} we have at our disposal that are $P = \alpha N$. Keeping a fixed number of neurons N then the large α is the larger the number of parameters in the fit will be. Based on previous results on RC one would expect that the readout weights would just decrease with α . We can measure the relative change in the synaptic matrix as a ratio of matrix norms i.e. $\delta = \frac{\|\mathbf{W}\|}{\|\mathbf{W}_{out}\|}$. Fig. 5 shows this measure $\delta(\alpha, g)$ averaged over 20 different realization for each point in the plane. While it is generally true that $\delta(\alpha, g)$ decreases for larger α , when the load α is fixed and g is varied we can find perturbations that differs by orders of magnitude.

Figure 5. Figure a) demonstrates that the size of the learned synaptic matrix $\tilde{\mathbf{W}}$ with respect to the original symmetric matrix \mathbf{W} largely varies in the plane (α, g) . For each value in the plane we perform the training of the Lorenz attractor and computed $\delta = |\tilde{\mathbf{W}}|/|\mathbf{W}|$ averaged over 20 different realizations. On b) we report a portion of the original matrix and the learned perturbation in two cases: $\alpha = 0.2$ and $1/g = 3$ (cyan star) and $\alpha = 0.75$ and $1/g = 2$ (green star).

Comparing this findings with that of Fig. 2 we can conclude that the smaller the attractor complexity the larger the perturbation must be to perform a good fit. Note that if the perturbation is too large the reference minimum, around which the dynamics in the driven phase develops, will most likely lose its stability in autonomous phase explaining the low success rate in reproduction.

3.6 Multiple task hosted by independent attractor states

Historically the memories of attractor network are the minima of the energy-landscape. We have shown however that it is possible to reproduce complex dynamical systems close to those minima and that the cost in terms of synaptic perturbation is relatively small. Consequently it should be possible to 'store' multiple dynamical systems in different attractors and recall them based on the initial conditions. The appeal of this paradigm is evident. Context depend behaviour is a key element of intelligent systems. Several studies have showed that vanilla reservoir are indeed capable of reproducing multiple dynamical system given a context signal. This is a crucial element because typical reservoir RNN work close to a potentially unstable unique fixed point hence a bias is necessary to distinguish the different cases. The idea of a constant context signal is rather unrealistic for at least two reasons. First keeping the bias signal always on has a considerable cost for any kind of system. Secondly the brain is capable of switching context with an almost instantaneous cue. There are also technical problems in storing multiple dynamical system in standard RNN, in fact the insurgence of chimera states, i.e. trajectories that are mixtures of the desired dynamics, has been reported as an open problem. Our paradigm present a simple solution to both problems. Indeed by storing different target dynamics to different minima, which are sufficiently far apart in the phase space, cross-talk noise should be minimized and moreover there is no need of context signal in fact the context is simply the initial condition of the network. While we leave a systematic investigation for future work we show Fig. 6 a particularly interesting successful case where we reproduce three different chaotic systems close to three different attractors. Note that here the readout matrix here is unique and not the sum of three low rank matrices as typically done with vanilla RNN. The advantage here is that there is no need to chose the right readout given the context.

4 Conclusions

This study investigated the feasibility of reservoir computing using a recurrent neural network (RNN) with symmetric couplings, specifically the Hopfield model. Our primary aim was to determine whether high-dimensionality and the asymmetric nature of the synaptic matrix \mathbf{W} are essential for effective emulation of dynamical systems. We found that attractor neural networks can be used for reservoir computing, eliminating the need for chaos and asymmetry. Leveraging the analytical tractability of these networks we developed a complete theory that explains the inner workings. The properties of the energy landscape were crucial for determining whether the reservoir could autonomously reproduce the target system. Not all attractors were suitable for reservoir computing. The roughness or complexity of the local energy landscape, measured by the coefficient of variation of the eigenvalues ($c_v(\lambda)$), was a key predictor of success. High complexity in the attractor landscape facilitated better performance in reproducing chaotic trajectories, such as those of the Lorenz system. At the same time the more complex the attractor was the smaller the perturbation synaptic coupling after training was. The general idea on how these systems learn how to mimic arbitrary dynamics is that any dynamical system can be recast as a gradient system with a time-dependent drive. In the driven phase the signal modifies both the position and topology of the reference attractor moving the 'center of mass'. The

Figure 6. Using a single readout, J_r in gray in the figure, it is possible to train the RNN to reproduce three different chaotic systems depending on the initial condition. The network dynamics unfolds close to three attractors, colored dots in a), of the original associative network. Figure a) shows the post-training autonomous dynamics in the a reduce overlaps m space. In b) the time course of some overlaps for the 3 different initial conditions where the gray lines indicate the position of the original reference attractor. Finally using the same readouts, see c), on $\tilde{m}(t)$ for the 3 different cases we are able to faithfully reproduce the 3 attractors in their original space.

system at each time step will follow this movement by following the gradient in a way akin to gravitational systems. Once the loop is closed this picture continues to hold, hence we were able to predict before learning the success rate and to understand the reasons behind failure. Historically, attractor network memories are the minima of the energy landscape. However, we demonstrated that it is possible to reproduce complex dynamical systems close to these minima with relatively small synaptic perturbation. This suggests that multiple dynamical systems can be stored in different attractors and recalled based on initial conditions, offering context-dependent behavior crucial for intelligent systems.

Vanilla reservoirs have shown the capability to reproduce multiple dynamical systems but a continuous bias signal acting as a context, which is costly and unrealistic. Our paradigm, storing different dynamics in distinct minima, minimizes cross-talk noise and eliminates the need for such a bias, with the initial network conditions serving as the context. In conclusion, our study highlights the potential of symmetric recurrent neural networks in reservoir computing, offering insights into their dynamics, learning processes, and practical applications. Moreover with this work we built a bridge between two important ideas at the foundation of theoretical neuroscience namely attractor neural network and reservoir computing. Future work will explore the broader implications of these findings, aiming to integrate attractor neural networks more deeply into machine learning frameworks.

5 Methods

TBA ...

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